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Complexes of Some Platinum Metals with 4-Amino-3,5-Dimercapto-1,2,4-Triazole

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In a previous communication¹ the complexes of some bivalent metal ions with 4-amino-3,5-dimercapto-1,2,4-triazole (H_2AMT) were reported. In the present communication we are reporting the preparation and characterisation of complexes of Ru(II), Rh(III), Pd(II) and Pt(II) with H_2AMT .

Experimental

Preparation of complexes: $M(HAMT)_2$, ($M = Pd^{2+}$ or Pt^{2+}): An aqueous ethanolic solution of metal chloride (1.0%, ~50 ml) was treated with pyridine dropwise to get a light yellow solution of $[M(Py)_4]Cl_2$. The resulting solution of tetrapyridino complex was refluxed on a steam bath with an excess of ligand (1 : 2.5 molar ratio) in ethanolic solution when almost insoluble precipitate of the bis chelated complex separated out. The product was collected on a filter, washed with ethanol and dried in air (yield almost quantitative).

[Ru($HAMT$)₂]: An ethanolic solution of ruthenium(II) chloride² (1.0%, 50 ml) was refluxed with an excess of ligand (1 : 2.5 molar ratio) for half an hour when a dark green precipitate began to separate slowly. The product was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in air. Yield about 70–80%.

[Rh($HAMT$)₂.Cl.H₂O]: An ethanolic solution of hydrated rhodium(III) chloride (2.0%, 50 ml) was refluxed with excess of ligand on a steam bath by adjusting pH to 2-3 with dilute hydrochloric acid for about 1 hr. The chloro complex $[Rh(HAMT)_2.Cl.H_2O]$ separated as brick red precipitate. The product was collected on a filter, washed with ethanol and dried as usual.

[Rh₂(AMT)₃]: The complex was obtained as insoluble orange red precipitate, when an ethanolic solution of hydrated rhodium(III) chloride (pH 5-6) was refluxed with 1 : 2 molar ratio of ligand on a steam bath for about 1 hr.

The ligand was prepared as reported earlier¹. The platinum metal chlorides were obtained from Johnson and Mathey Ltd.

The analytical results and electronic reflectance or absorption bands of complexes with their tentative assignments are shown in Table 1.

Magnetic susceptibilities and electronic spectra of the complexes were measured as reported earlier¹. Infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded in KBr disc on a Perkin Elmer 577 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The analytical results of complexes (Table 1) show that 4-amino-3,5-dimercapto-1,2,4-triazole (A) forms complexes with tautomeric forms B and C.

The attempt to prepare Ru(III) and Pt(IV) complexes was unsuccessful since they were reduced by the ligand to Ru(II) and Pt(II) respectively. The complexes of $HAMT^-$ as well as AMT^{2-} are almost soluble in ethanol and water but are sparingly soluble in DMF or dioxane. The poor solubility of the complexes indicates their polymeric nature. The complexes are diamagnetic, indicating four coordinated square planar structure for Pd(II) and Pt(II) while octahedral for Rh(III) and Ru(II) in these complexes. The solid reflectance spectrum of $Rh(HAMT)_2.Cl.H_2O$ displays shoulders near 470 nm and 340 nm assignable to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g} + CT$ transitions (Table 1) in octahedral environment of rhodium(III) ions^{3,4}. The reflectance spectrum of $Ru(HAMT)_2$ displays a broad and weak band near 570-580 nm assignable to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$ transition, similar to hexa-coordinated Ru(II) complexes^{5,6}. The other d-d transition of Ru(II) complex could not be observed due to strong charge transfer absorption. In solid state $[Pd(HAMT)_2]$ shows a shoulder near 500 nm, while in solution it shows a number of bands between 350 and 200 nm (Table 1) attributable to ligand field and charge transfer bands⁷. Reflectance spectrum of $[Pt(HAMT)_2]$ displays a shoulder near 400 nm assignable to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ transition⁷ in square planar field.

The assignment of ir spectral bands of H_2AMT and its complexes has been reported previously¹. In the present investigation it is found that NH_2 and NH stretching vibrations of the ligand in the complexes are not well resolved, rather it is observed as a broad and medium band near $3130 \pm 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The NH_2 deformation vibrations (Table 2) of ligand are also shifted to higher frequencies suggesting the bonding of NH_2 nitrogen in these complexes. The thioamide bands (I to IV) of ligand are affected appreciably in complexes and are observed as broad and medium to weak bands in AMT^{2-} complexes, and as well resolved and

TABLE 1

Complex (colour)	%Metal Found (Calcd.)	%N Found (Calcd.)	%C Found (Calcd.)	%H Found (Calcd.)	Electronic band positions (nm)	Assignments
Pd(HAMT) ₂ (Deep red)	26.38 (26.55)	27.75 (27.95)	11.79 (11.98)	1.64 (1.49)	500 318* 266 257 252 208 400	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _{1g} ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ E _g ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _{1u} ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ A _{2u} ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ E _u π→π* ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _{1g}
Pt(HAMT) ₂ (Dull yellow)	39.72 (39.86)	22.83 (22.88)	9.74 (9.81)	1.42 (1.22)		
Ru(HAMT) ₂ (Deep green)	25.10 (25.43)	23.07 (23.18)	12.20 (12.09)	2.35 (2.01)	570 sh -580	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{2g}
Rh(HAMT) ₂ .Cl.H ₂ O** (Brick red)	22.44 (22.73)	24.57 (24.74)	—	—	470 sh 340 sh	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{2g} ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{1g} +CT
Rh ₂ (AMT) ₃ (Orange red)	31.56 (31.65)	25.34 (25.33)	11.20 (11.08)	1.75 (1.84)	465 sh	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{2g}

* Absorption band in ethanol. ** Percent of halogen ; Found : 7.53 ; Calcd. : 7.83.

TABLE 2—IR BANDS IN cm⁻¹

H ₂ AMT	[M(HAMT) ₂] H=Pd ²⁺ , Pt ²⁺ , Ru ²⁺	Rh ₂ (AMT) ₃	Rh(HAMT) ₂ .Cl.H ₂ O	Assignments
—	—	—	3440 wb 3140 mb	ν(OH) of H ₂ O ν(NH ₂) + ν(NH)
3285 msp 3110 — 2650 sb 2110 wb 1608 s	3120 ± 10 mb — 2930 ± 5 wb — 1620 ± 10 m	3150 m — — 1615 sb	— — 2940 sh — 1610 sh 1585 sb	— — — — ν(S-H) δ(NH ₂) + δ(H ₂ O)
1510 s 1472 sh 1325 m 1255 sb 1018 s 940 vs	1520 ± 5 m 1485 ± 5 m 1390 ± 10 mb 1270 ± 5 m 1060 ± 10 w 980 ± 5 w	— 1498 mb 1400 sh 1300 sb 1060 wb	— 1485 sb 1390 sh 1290 sb 1040 m 980 sb 835 wb 720 mb — 640 mb 422 wb 335 w	Thioamide band I Thioamide band II β(NH ₂) Thioamide band III Thioamide band IV (H ₂ O) ν(C-S) contribution
750 wb 725 ms 645 s — —	740 ± 10 w 695 ± 5 vs 620 ± 5 s — 360 ± 20 w	748 m 675 mb 620 wb 433 m 325 sh	— — — — —	Ring stretch ν(M-N) stretch ν(M-S) stretch

s=strong ; m=medium ; b=broad ; w=weak ; sh=shoulder ; sp=sharp.

medium to strong bands in HAMT⁻ complexes. The thioamide band IV located at 940 cm⁻¹ almost disappears in AMT²⁻ complexes but is observed with reduced intensity at 980 ± 5 cm⁻¹ in HAMT⁻ complexes, indicating that one of the thione sulphur is free in monoanionic ligand. A weak band located at 750 cm⁻¹ in free ligand attributable to ν(C-S) vibration is shifted to lower frequencies in all complexes. Thus it is inferred from the nature of shift of thioamide bands that one thioamide deprotonated thiol sulphur is coordinated in HAMT⁻ while both the thioamide deprotonated thiol sulphur are bonded to AMT²⁻ complexes. A broad band at 835 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra of [Rh(HAMT)₂.Cl.H₂O] can be attributed to out of plane deformation vibration of coordinated water.

In far infrared region, a weak band (320-380 cm⁻¹) observed in a few complexes has been tentatively

suggested to ν(M-S) vibration. The reduced intensity of ν(M-S) vibration is attributed to the polymeric nature of the complexes. The observed range of ν(M-S) vibration is well within the range of metal-sulphur stretching frequencies of S-bonded transition metal complexes with sulphur donor ligands^{10,11}.

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Donor Properties of Ditertiaryphosphine Dioxides towards Iron(III)

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COORDINATION chemistry of bifunctional organophosphorus ligands, namely, ditertiaryphosphine dioxides towards various metal ions has been reported¹. However, there are known only two complexes with iron(III), viz., [Fe(MBDPO)₂](ClO₄)₃ and [Fe(MBDPO)₂][FeCl₄]₃ (MBDPO = 1,1-methylenebis(dibutylphosphine oxide)). It was therefore considered worthwhile to study the coordination properties of bidentate ditertiaryphosphine dioxides (I) involving phenyl substituents on phosphorus towards iron(II) and iron(III).

The intention was to study the effect of ring size on stability and nature of complexes by increasing the number of methylene groups and using Mössbauer spectrometer as one of techniques for structure elucidation. In this communication, we are reporting complexes of 1,1-methylenebis(diphenylphosphine oxide) (MDPO), 1,2-dimethylenebis(diphenylphosphine oxide) (EDPO), 1,4-tetramethylenebis(diphenylphosphine oxide) (BDPO) and 1,6-hexamethylenebis(diphenylphosphine oxide) (HDPO) with chloride, bromide, nitrate and perchlorate of iron(III). These have been characterised by elemental analysis, molar conductance, ir and reflectance spectra.

Experimental

The ligands MDPO, EDPO, BDPO and HDPO were prepared by oxidation of the corresponding ditertiaryphosphines with hydrogen peroxide (Lit. m.p. MDPO, 176-178°; EDPO, 256-58°; BDPO, 246-47° and HDPO, 196-97°)².

The complexes were prepared by the interaction of iron(III) salts with the ligands in suitable solvents. The solid products were obtained either on gentle heating or on subsequent treatment with petroleum ether (40-60°). Iron was estimated spectrophotometrically³. Carbon and hydrogen were analysed in University College of Sciences, Calcutta. The molar conductances of millimolar solutions of complexes in nitrobenzene were measured with Toshniwal Type CLOI/02A conductivity bridge. The ir spectra of the ligands and the complexes were recorded in the range 4600-650 cm⁻¹ in nujol mulls using Spectromom-2000. The reflectance spectra of the complexes in the range

TABLE 1—THE ELEMENTAL ANALYSES AND SPECTRAL PROPERTIES OF COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Complex	Analysis % ; Found, (Calcd.)			m.p. (°C)	$\nu(\text{PO})$ cm ⁻¹	λ_{max} nm
		C	H	Fe			
1.	FeCl ₃ .MDPO	50.80 (51.80)	4.39 (3.91)	10.43 (9.68)	268	1145 (s, sp) 1140 (w)	330 (m, sp), 430 (b, s), 520 (sh)
2.	FeCl ₃ .BDPO	55.53 (54.10)	5.08 (4.50)	8.82 (9.02)	212	1146 (s, sp) 1162 (s, sp)	360 (sh), 380 (s, sp), 400 (w)
3.	FeCl ₃ .HDPO.H ₂ O	54.32 (54.01)	5.19 (5.10)	8.31 (8.40)	112	1139 (s, sp)	360 (sh), 380 (s, sp), 430 (s, sp), 400 (w)
4.	[Fe(MDPO) ₂](ClO ₄) ₃ .H ₂ O	54.58 (55.53)	3.90 (4.19)	3.75 (3.45)	300	1172 (m, sp)	350 (s, sp), 510 (w, b)
5.	[Fe(EDPO) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ [(ClO ₄) ₂]	51.86 (50.62)	4.09 (4.05)	4.52 (4.54)	262	1.38 (s, sp)	330 (sh), 360 (s, sp)
6.	[Fe(BDPO)(ac) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ .ClO ₄	44.46 (43.90)	3.48 (3.60)	6.18 (6.39)	210(d)	1170 (s, sp)	350 (s, sp), 370 (sh)
7.	[Fe ₂ (MDPO) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄].[NO ₃] ₂ .2H ₂ O	50.14 (50.81)	4.65 (3.95)	6.52 (6.33)	221(d)	1154 (s, sp) 1170 (m, sp)	370 (sh), 390 (s, sp), 490 (w), 570 (w)
8.	[Fe(EDPO) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂].[NO ₃] ₂ .H ₂ O	55.10 (55.71)	3.54 (4.46)	5.49 (5.00)	264	1140 (s, sp) 1170 (sh)	380 (s, sp), 430 (w), 460 (s, sp)
9.	Fe(NO ₃) ₃ .BDPO	47.43 (48.00)	—	3.40 (8.00)	121	1134 (s, sp)	380 (s, sp), 430 (w), 460 (s, sp)
10.	FeBr ₃ .BDPO	44.01 (44.50)	3.46 (3.60)	7.96 (7.42)	206	1139 (s, sp) 1150 (s, sp)	380 (sh), 420 (w), 490 (s, sp), 540 (w)

d = decomposition ; s = strong ; m = medium ; sp = sharp ; sh = shoulder ; w = weak ; ac = acetone.

The ir spectra show the presence of lattice water in complexes.